

atom attached to S-atom was not observed probably due to its presence in the negative region. [Rh(HATU)(TPP)Cl] gives signals at τ 6.3 ($H\beta_1 + H\beta_2$), 5.4 (H_α), 2.7 (phenyl proton) and 0.91 (H_γ) in the intensity ratio of 4 : 1 : 15 : 1. For [Rh(HNMATU)(TPP)Cl], the signals are at τ 7.3 (CH_3), 7.0 (H_α), 6.0 ($H\beta_1 + H\beta_2$), 2.7 (phenyl) and 1 (H_γ), having the intensity ratio of 3 : 1 : 3 : 15 : 1. The appearance of these signals indicates the presence of a strong ring-current in the metal chelate ring.

From the above discussion it is concluded that Rh^{III} forms SN bonded octahedral complexes while Rh^I forms square-planar complexes with the ligands and TPP.

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The Thermodynamic Dissociation Constant of $MgSO_4$ in 10% Dioxane – Water Solution at 308.15 K

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Manuscript received 16 August 1988, revised 15 September 1988, accepted 4 October 1988

A study of the thermodynamics of dissociation of the sulphates of bivalent metals in aquo-organic media requires the determination of the dissociation constant of the sulphates at a number of temperatures.

Dissociation constant (K) of $MgSO_4$ in dioxane – water mixed solvent of various dioxane content has been determined by Mason and Shutt¹ at 293.15 K from dielectric constant measurements. Dunsmore and James² determined K at 298.15 K in 10 and 20% dioxane content of dioxane – water mixed solvent from conductivity measurements.

These values of K are likely to be less accurate than the values obtained from e m f. measurements with cells having no liquid junction potential which is now established to give the most accurate values

for the dissociation constant of electrolytes. Hence both cells (C-1) and (C-2) were set up.

Experimental

H_2SO_4 , $MgSO_4$ and HCl used were all of G.R. grade. Three stock solutions of $MgSO_4$ and H_2SO_4 in water in molal ratio 5 : 1, 3 : 1 and 1 : 1 respectively and another stock solution of $MgSO_4$ and HCl in equimolar proportion were prepared. These were then appropriately mixed with water and then dioxane to prepare solutions of known molality in 10% (w/w) dioxane of the mixed solvent. The solutions were deoxygenated and filled in cells as described previously. The setting up of the all-glass cell, thermostat, e m f. assembly etc were as described earlier³. The cells came to equilibrium quickly but e.m.f. readings were taken after 2 h of the introduction of the cells in the thermostat, at intervals of 0.5 h for at least 1.5 h over which the e.m.f. readings of the duplicate cells remained constant within 0.02 mV. The mean of the two e.m.f. readings after correcting for barometric pressure, vapour pressure and bubbler depth was recorded.

Results and Discussion

The e.m.f. of cell (C-1) is given by equation (1),

$$E = E^0 - \frac{k}{2} \log m_H^2 m_{SO_4} \nu_H^2 \nu_{SO_4} \quad (1)$$

which reduces to equation (2) since it has been established that modified Davies equation is valid in this case⁴.

$$E = E^0 - \frac{k}{2} \log m_H^2 m_{SO_4} + \frac{3k A \sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - \frac{k}{2} \beta_1 \mu \quad (2)$$

where, $k = 2.3026 RT/F$, A = appropriate Debye – Hückel constant, and $\beta_1 = 2\beta_H + \beta_{SO_4}$.

If we assume that Hg_2SO_4 is completely dissociated then Scheme 1 should represent the equilibria present in the solution of cell (C-1) and equations (3), (4) and (5) should hold.

Scheme 1

NOTES

$$m_H \cdot m_{H_2SO_4} = m_1^2(1 - \alpha^2) \quad (3)$$

$$(m_{SO_4})_T = (m_{SO_4})_{H_2SO_4} + (m_{SO_4})_{MgSO_4} + (m_{SO_4})_{Hg_2SO_4} \quad (4)$$

$$\log \frac{m_H m_{SO_4}}{m_{H_2SO_4}} = \log K_2 + \frac{4A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - \beta_2 \mu \quad (5)$$

where values of $\log K_2$, the dissociation constant of H_2SO_4 and β_2 are known⁵ (for 10% dioxane at 308.15 K these values are 3.87 and 0.4 mol⁻¹ kg respectively). Now assuming an arbitrary value of μ we get the value of $m_H \cdot m_{SO_4}$ from equation (2) and $m_H \cdot m_{SO_4} / m_{H_2SO_4}$ from equation (5) and hence value of $m_1^2(1 - \alpha^2)$ from equation (3). Since the value of m_1 is known, we get values of m_H and $m_{H_2SO_4}$ and hence of $(m_{SO_4})_T$ from equation (5). Solubility product (K_{sp}) of Hg_2SO_4 is related to ionic strength of the solution by equation (6),

$$\log m_{Hg_2} \cdot m_{SO_4} = \log K_{sp} + \frac{8A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - \beta_3 \mu \quad (6)$$

and μ , the ionic strength of the solution is given by equation (7),

$$\mu = m_1 + 4(m_{SO_4})_T - 2(m_{SO_4})_{H_2SO_4} \quad (7)$$

Values of $\log K_{sp}$ and β_3 have been found by us following the method of Sharma and Prasad⁶ over a number of temperatures. At 308.15 K for 10% dioxane these values are 7.619 and 0.8 mol⁻¹ kg respectively.

m_{MgSO_4} turned out to be negative. For $m_2/m_1 = 3$ or 5 the iteration could not be carried out to completion as m_{Mg} became $> m_2$ at a certain stage of iteration) at all the three relative values of m_1 and m_2 except at very low values of m_1 and m_2 ($\mu < 0.003$ mol kg⁻¹) possibly because one or all of the following assumptions made were not quite correct: (i) $\gamma_H = \gamma_{H_2SO_4}$, (ii) $\gamma_{Hg} = \gamma_{SO_4}$, (iii) complete dissociation of Hg_2SO_4 . So cell (C-1) was abandoned.

The e.m.f. of cell (C-2) will be given by equation (10). The e.m.f. and the relevant data are given in Table 1.

$$E = E^\circ - k \log m_H \cdot m_{Cl} + \frac{2kA\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} - k\beta\mu \quad (10)$$

The equilibria present in the solution of cell (C-2) will be given by Scheme 2 since we may justifiably assume that $MgCl_2$ is completely dissociated⁸ in dioxane-water media of less than 30% dioxane content.

Scheme 2

The ionic strength μ of the solution will be given by equation (12),

$$\mu = 3m_1 + 4m_{SO_4} - 2m_H \quad (12)$$

TABLE 1—E.M.F. AND MOLALITIES OF IONS IN CELL (C-2)*

Temp. = 308.15 K, $\alpha = 10$

m_{HCl}	$(m_{MgSO_4})_T$	E obs. V	m_H	$m_{H_2SO_4}$	m_{SO_4}	m_{Mg}	μ	K_o $\times 10^3$	q
0.002 819	0.004 183	0.527 50	0.002 415	0.000 804	0.001 476	0.001 780	0.009 348	1.093	4.599
0.004 731	0.004 839	0.500 54	0.004 238	0.000 493	0.001 497	0.001 990	0.011 704	1.045	4.531
0.005 379	0.005 533	0.495 89	0.004 613	0.000 766	0.002 322	0.003 088	0.016 200	2.933	4.903
0.006 555	0.006 741	0.480 00	0.005 337	0.001 218	0.003 544	0.004 762	0.023 163	8.530	3.271
0.006 555	0.006 741	0.498 23	0.005 308	0.001 346	0.003 674	0.004 921	0.023 745	9.933	3.330
0.008 450	0.006 796	0.474 97	0.006 881	0.001 569	0.003 684	0.005 253	0.026 322	12.542	3.400
0.007 510	0.008 605	0.483 87	0.005 717	0.001 797	0.005 462	0.007 255	0.032 945	29.353	3.699
0.011 207	0.011 527	0.465 80	0.003 034	0.003 173	0.007 971	0.011 144	0.049 438	232.196	2.456

*All concentrations and ionic strengths are in mol kg⁻¹.

Following the iteration procedure used by Prasad and Ghosh⁷ values of m_{Mg} , m_{SO_4} and m_{MgSO_4} could be found out. Putting these values in equation (8), the value of dissociation constant K could be

$$K_o = \frac{m_{Mg} \cdot m_{SO_4}}{m_{MgSO_4}} \quad (8)$$

found graphically from equation (9) from a plot of q against μ .

$$q = \log K_o - \frac{8A\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + \sqrt{\mu}} = \log K - \beta_2 \mu \quad (9)$$

However, the method failed in this case (for $m_2/m_1 = 1$, a constant μ was obtained after iteration but

Now assuming an arbitrary value of μ , we find out the value of m_H from equation (10), since $m_{Cl} = m_1$ is known. Knowing value of m_H we can find m_{MgSO_4} and m_{SO_4} from equation (11). When these values are fed in equation (12) we get a fresh value of μ . The iteration is continued till we get constant value of μ and hence of m_H , $m_{H_2SO_4}$ and m_{SO_4} upto 10 micromol kg⁻¹. These values give K_o and hence q of equations (8) and (9). A plot of q against μ is linear, the points deviating from linearity within 0.1 mV. The intercept of the plot at $\mu = 0$ gives the value of $\log K$ and the slope gives the value of β_2 . These values are $pK = 3.89 \pm 0.01$ and -48.0 ± 0.1 in kg mol⁻¹. Since the cell gives quite satisfactory

results the cell might be explored to find out the pK values of MgSO₄ at other temperatures.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (A. G.) thanks C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for the grant of Senior Research Fellowship.

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Classical Coulomb Energies $J_L(\rho)$ and $J_{NL}(\rho)$ of an Atomic Charge Distribution. Studies with a Two-parameter Charge Density Function

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Manuscript received 14 December 1987, revised 18 April 1988, accepted 2 November 1988

THE present work is devoted to estimate the coulomb energies for first row of atoms under local and non-local approximations. In view of this, two-parameter statistical model for atoms suggested by Gazquez and Parr¹ has been used under density function formalism. It is seen that the gradient correction to the kinetic energy is necessary for the estimation of these values.

During the few years there has been a lot of interest in the density functional approach to interpret the chemical and physical properties of atomic and molecular systems in terms of density, and it is highly desirable to use this quantity as a basic variable in quantum chemistry. Yet no theory has been developed to relate electron density directly to other quantities like energy, satisfactorily. For this, some kind of approximation has to be made.

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Some of these lead to the results which are comparable with the Hartree-Fock values in some respect. In many cases they give poor and unphysical results.

Many attempts have been made, using various models, like Thomas-Fermi² model and its extension give considerable insight into the properties of true electronic systems.

The main interest in density-functional description of the electronic structure of an atom is the classical repulsion between electronic charge distribution and itself, given as

$$J(\rho) = 1/2 \iint \frac{\rho(\mathbf{r}_1)\rho(\mathbf{r}_2)}{r_{12}} d\mathbf{r}_1 d\mathbf{r}_2 \quad (1)$$

where, ρ is the total electron density for an atom in its ground state. It is also quite interesting to make the approximation to $J(\rho)$ and the equivalent from of equation (1) (already proposed³ and studied⁴ in detail) is the so-called local approximation, given by

$$J_L(\rho) = B_0 N^{2/3} \int \rho^{4/3} d\tau \quad (2)$$

where, B_0 is the universal constant and N the number of electrons.

In the present paper, the form of the density function used is given by

$$\rho(\gamma) = \frac{C}{(A+\gamma)^{2n}} \quad (3)$$

where, C is the normalisation constant, and A and n are variational parameters determined by the minimisation of the total energy. An energy-density functional with gradient correction upto fourth order in kinetic energy is

$$E(\rho) = T_0(\rho) + T_2(\rho) + V_{ne}(\rho) + V_{ee}(\rho) + \frac{K(\rho) + T_4(\rho)}{K(\rho) + T_4(\rho)} \quad (4)$$

where,

$$T_0(\rho) = \left(\frac{3}{10}\right) (3\pi^2)^{2/3} \int \rho^{5/3}(\gamma) d\tau$$

$$T_2(\rho) = \frac{1}{8} \int \frac{(\nabla\rho)^2}{\rho} d\tau$$

$$T_4(\rho) = \frac{(3\pi^2)^{-2/3}}{540}$$

$$\left[\int \left[\rho^{1/3} \left(\frac{\nabla\rho}{\rho}\right)^2 - \frac{9}{8} \left(\frac{\nabla\rho}{\rho}\right) \left(\frac{\nabla\rho}{\rho}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{\nabla\rho}{\rho}\right)^4 \right] d\tau \right]$$

$$V_{ee}(\rho) = 0.4702 \int \rho^{4/3}(\gamma) d\tau$$

$$k(\rho) = \beta_1 Z^{2/3} \int \rho^{4/3}(\gamma) d\tau$$

$$V_{ne}(\rho) = -Z \int \rho(\gamma) d\tau$$

We have used the two-parameter statistical model of Gazquez and Parr to estimate the classical coulomb energies of first row of atoms and the results are reported here. We have used the following three different energy-density functionals for obtaining the two-parameter charge density distributions: model-I: an energy-density functional similar to the Thomas-Fermi density (TFD) model^{5,6} (i.e. Eqn. 4 without $T_2(\rho)$ and $T_4(\rho)$ terms); model-II: simple TFD model with